

A market and financial feasibility analysis as preparation for the production of shampoo bar

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Abstract

More people are worried about the environmental harm caused by plastic waste, so there is an increased need for eco-friendly options in personal care items. This study examined the market and financial feasibility of producing Essentiels Shampoo Bar, which is an organic and plastic-free hair product, in Barangays Talon I and Talon II of Las Piñas City. A descriptive-quantitative approach was used, based on survey responses from 382 people. These participants were chosen using Slovin's formula to ensure a 5% margin of error. The study determined consumer preferences, projected demand and supply, pricing structure, and profitability. The results showed that the market has a strong acceptability, with 76% of people saying they would use organic shampoo bars and 70% saying they would be willing to pay between ₱151 and ₱200 for them. Demand projections showed a big and growing demand–supply gap, which means the market is a good time to enter. The financial analysis showed a predicted profit margin of about 49%, which means the business is likely to be very profitable and economically sound. The results show that it is possible to introduce Essentiels Shampoo Bar as a good and eco-friendly option in the local market.

Keywords: Shampoo bar; Market; Financial feasibility analysis; Production; Profitability.

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Introduction

Plastic pollution is now one of the largest environmental issues in the world, as the use of single-use plastics in everyday products has been common nowadays, especially in packaging for personal care items (Parker, 2019; Rhein & Schmid, 2020). Most liquid shampoos come in plastic bottles, and a lot of these bottles are not being recycled properly. This results in more waste being thrown away in landfills and causing damage to the oceans (Isangedighi et al., 2019; Kosior & Crescenzi, 2020).

People are starting to worry more about the environment, and because of that, they are buying more products that are better for the planet in an attempt to help protect nature. Green consumerism is when people decide to buy products in a way that is better for the environment. They look for products that are made in a sustainable way, as they come from ethical sources and have less harmful impact on the planet (Akenji, 2014; Luchs et al., 2010; Young et al., 2010). This change has brought about new ideas in the cosmetics industry, particularly in the personal care industry, like creating solid shampoo bars.

Shampoo bars are solid products that clean your hair without needing plastic bottles. These products often have less water and are advertised as being more environmentally friendly, when compared to usual liquid shampoos (Ho, 2019; Ogle, 2016). People who care about the environment are more likely

to choose personal care products that are friendly to the planet, are of good quality, and are not too expensive in different markets (Barbarossa & De Pelsmacker, 2016; Klaschka et al., 2006).

The idea of using resources in a sustainable way has become more important. People's buying choices for eco-friendly products depend on how much they care about the environment. They care a lot about the environment and believe that their actions can really make a difference. They think that even small changes can help protect the planet and improve the world for future generations (Cooper-Ordoñez et al., 2019; Paparoidamis & Tran, 2019). People who see environmental problems as essential issues are more likely to choose greener options.

Essentiels Shampoo Bar is a soap-like shampoo product that you can carry with you every day. Our shampoo bar contains different natural ingredients (coconut oil, olive oil, castor oil, lye, water, tea tree oil, rosemary oil, and peppermint oil) that is good for up to 45 to 50 washes. This handy version of shampoo is made of organic ingredients. It does not contain any harmful chemical that comes with the existing shampoo products. The shampoo is easier to store and easier to reuse because it dries up just like soap. Our product is 30% cheaper than the leading shampoo brand because it does not require the use of plastic materials.

Because of these trends, launching Essentiels Shampoo Bar aligns with global efforts to be more eco-friendly and matches the way people behave and decide. The Essentiels Shampoo Bar is a fully natural shampoo that cleanses your hair. It comes in a tin container that can be recycled, and it does not contain any plastic. The study aims to see if it is feasible to make this product in Barangays Talon I and Talon II, Las Piñas City, by looking at market demand, supply conditions, and financial sustainability.

Methodology

This study used a descriptive-quantitative method to determine the feasibility to make a shampoo bar. The study was conducted in Barangays Talon I and Talon II, which are both in Las Piñas City. The total number of people who live in the selected barangays is 102,860. Using Slovin's formula and a 5% margin of error, the sample size was determined to be 382 individuals. A structured survey questionnaire was used to collect information on hair washing frequency, consumer preferences, awareness of shampoo bars, price sensitivity, and willingness to purchase organic products. Surveys were handed out to a group of people who were selected to join the study. Responses were tabulated and statistically analyzed using frequency and percentage distribution. The study utilized percentage analysis, growth rate computation (3% annual population growth), demand projection formula, supply growth estimation, and contribution margin analysis.

Customers

The proponents of this study agreed that the best and right location for the first company store will be open in Talon II, Las Piñas City, because it is a highly concentrated and highly populated location. Since it is located near a university, bank institutions and different companies, we expect that a lot of our customers will be students and young professionals. The proponents of this feasibility study will also market the product in different locations by joining different bazaars in Metro Manila. The total population of Talon II, Las Piñas City is 53,091 as of 2015 Census of Population.

Identification of Respondents

The researchers conducted a survey to realize how much potential Talon I and Talon II have in the market. To figure out the number of people from the target market, the researchers calculated the average population in the area where they planned to set up their business.

Table 1. Barangay Population

Talon I	Talon II	Total Population	Survey Percentage
41,144	61,716	102,860	100%

The researchers estimated the average population of consumers living within the location store. Given the population of 53,091 with the confidence level of 95% using the Slovene's formula the researchers conducted their survey.

Results and Discussion

Survey Analysis

The statistics below were gathered by the proponents through the use of their survey questionnaire for the feasibility study of Essentiels Shampoo Bar.

Table 2. Demographic Profile

Profile	Factors	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Range of Income	Php10,000-Php14,999	141	37%	2
	Php15,000-Above	241	63%	1
Gender	Male	135	35%	2
	Female	247	65%	1

Table 2 shows the demographic profile. In terms of range of income, it shows that most of the response for the income level would be at the range of Php15,000-above. This means that most of our target consumers came from middle-class-income earners. Meanwhile, in terms of gender, the above table shows that 65% of the respondents were females, while 35% of them were males. This is important for the company because it has a big impact on their product. It shows that women are the biggest group of customers for the company, and that is a positive thing because most people who buy cosmetics are women.

Survey Questions for Individual Consumers

Table 3 highlights the survey analysis of the shampoo bar. In question number 1, most of the respondents answered "Once a day" with a frequency of 320, followed by "Every other day" with a frequency of 45 and "Once every two or three day" with a frequency of 17. This signifies that the use of shampoo in our daily lives is vital and important. In question number 2, most of the respondents answered "Pantene Shampoo" with a frequency of 126, followed by "Dove Shampoo" with a frequency of 125, followed by "Head and Shoulders Shampoo" with a frequency of 61, followed by "Sunsilk Shampoo" with a frequency of 63 and "Mayumi Organics" with a frequency of 7. This signifies that the use of traditional shampoo is still rampant, that is why we are really eager to change this lifestyle. In question number 3, most of the respondents answered "Repair Damaged Hair" with a frequency of 148, followed by "Nourishing" with a frequency of 119 and "Anti-Dandruff" with a frequency of 115. This signifies that a lot of our consumers wants a shampoo that will repair their damaged hair.

Table 3. Survey Analysis (N=382)

Questions	Choices	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Q1. How often do you wash your hair?	Once a day	320	84%	1
	Every other day	45	12%	2
	Once every two or three days	17	4%	3
Q2. Which of the following brands do you often use?	Mayumi Organics	7	2%	5
	Sunsilk Shampoo	63	16%	4
	Pantene Shampoo	126	33%	1
	Head and Shoulder Shampoo	61	17%	3
	Dove Shampoo	125	32%	2
Q3. What type of shampoo do you prefer?	Anti-Dandruff	115	30%	3
	Repair Damaged Hair	148	39%	1
	Nourishing	119	31	2
Q4. Do you prefer two-in-one products or individual function products?	2-in-1 Products	310	81%	1
	Individual Products	58	15%	2
	I do not care	14	4%	3
Q5. You tend to purchase your hair products through?	Retail Shop	311	81%	1
	Direct Shop	34	9%	3
	Online Store	37	10%	2
Q6. Which of the following factors mainly affect your choice?	Price	41	11%	3
	Effect	178	46%	1
	Brand	163	43%	2
Q7. To what extent are you familiar with Shampoo Bar?	Very well and I have used it before.	102	27%	3
	Heard of, but I never used it yet.	127	33%	2
	I am not familiar with it, but I will give it a try.	153	40%	1
Q8. If you have used it before, how do you like it?	Very good	95	25%	2
	Good	7	2%	3
	Never used it yet	280	73%	1
Q9. Compared to the existing shampoo brand, what advantage do you think a shampoo bar might have?	Better effect	64	17%	2
	Lower Price	42	11%	3
	Natural	276	72%	1
Q10. On average, how much money would you spend to try for a 45 grams of Shampoo Bar?	Php 60.00-Php 150.00	78	20%	2
	Php 151.00-Php 200.00	264	70%	1
	Php 201.00-Php 250.00	40	10%	3
Q11. Would you be willing to use organic shampoo to save the environment?	Yes	289	76%	1
	No	19	5%	3
	Maybe	74	19%	2
Q12. Where did you source your information regarding the existence of a shampoo bar product?	Family	37	10%	3
	Friends	89	23%	2
	Social Media Platforms	256	67%	1

In question number 4, most of the respondents answered “2-in-1 Products” with a frequency of 310, followed by “Individual Products” with a frequency of 58 and “I do not care” with a frequency of 14. This signifies that the multi-purpose shampoo will be the next thing in the market. In question number 5, most of the respondents answered, “Retail Shop” with a frequency of 311, followed by “Online Store” with a frequency of 37 and “Direct Shop” with a frequency of 34. This signifies that placing our product in different retail outlet stores will be beneficial to our company’s success. In question number 6, most respondents answered, “Effect” with a frequency of 178, followed by “Brand” with a frequency of 163 and “Price” with a frequency of 41. This signifies that the effectiveness of the shampoo is the most sought reason why consumers buy their shampoo.

In question number 7, most of the respondents answered, “I am not familiar with it, but I will give it a try” with a frequency of 153, followed by “Heard of, but I never used it yet” with a frequency of 127 and “Very well and I have used it before” with a frequency number of 102. This indicates that most of our respondents are not yet aware of our existence, but soon the product will be introduced to the market with the help of our strong marketing techniques. In question number 8, most of the respondents answered “Never used it yet” with a frequency of 280, followed by “Very good” with a frequency of 95 and “Good”

with a frequency of 7. This signifies that most of the consumers who tried our shampoo bar are really satisfied with the product. In question number 9, most of the respondents answered “Natural” with a frequency of 276, followed by “Better effect” with a frequency of 64 and “Lower Price” with a frequency of 64. This signifies that most of the consumers want us to be more natural and organic.

In question number 10, most of the respondents answered “Php 151.00-Php 200.00” with a frequency of 264, followed by “Php 60.00-Php 150.00” with a frequency of 78 and “Php 201.00-Php 250.00” with a frequency of 40. This indicates that the ideal average price of our 45 grams shampoo bar is from ₱151.00-₱200.00. In question number 11, most of the respondents answered “Yes” with a frequency of 289, followed by “Maybe” with a frequency of 74 and “No” with a frequency of 19. This indicates that most of the respondents are willing to use our organic shampoo bar to save the environment. In question number 12, most of the respondents answered “Social Media Platforms” with a frequency of 256, followed by “Friends” with a frequency of 89 and “a. Family” with a frequency of 37. This signifies that most of the respondents are getting information in different social media platforms.

Demand

Historical Household Population

The proponents of the study determined the household historical population of Talon I and Talon II with a total population of 99,864 in 2018. We also asked the Barangay Hall Department of the two barangays on the historical population from 2014 up to 2018 so we can get the average growth per year for the last five years.

Table 4. Historical Population (From Barangay Secretary of Talon 1 and Talon 2)

Year	Household Population		Total	Growth Rate
	Talon I	Talon II		
2014	35,459	53,188	88,647	
2015	35,756	53,633	89,389	1%
2016	38,053	57,078	95,131	3%
2017	39,182	58,773	97,955	3%
2018	39,946	59,918	99,864	2%
				Average: 3%

$$\text{Growth Rate} = ((\text{Present} - \text{Past}) \div \text{Past}) \times 100$$

Projected Population

The proponents of this feasibility study projected the population of Talon II for the next five years to determine the demand expected for Essentiels Shampoo Bars.

Table 5. Projected Population

Year	Growth Rate	Growth Per Year	Household Population		Projected Population
			Talon I	Talon II	
2018			39,946	59,918	99,864
2019	3%	2,996	41,144	61,716	102,860
2020	3%	3,086	42,378	63,568	105,946
2021	3%	3,178	43,650	65,474	109,124
2022	3%	3,274	44,959	67,439	112,398
2023	3%	3,372	46,308	69,462	115,770

In this table, it shows the increasing population of Talon I and Talon II per year. They have 3% household growth rate per year.

Projected Demand

Table 6 shows how the company’s growth will look over the next five years. To figure out the demand for the product, we calculated the number of expected household customers (99,864). This was done by multiplying the total number of households by the market acceptability rate, which is 76%, and then by the frequency agreement rate, which is 40%. Overall results will be multiplied by 4 weeks and then multiplied by 12 months to find the yearly total. In the following years, the product formula stays the same. The expected number of customers who will buy the Essentiels Shampoo Bar is calculated by multiplying the total number of respondents by the percentage of those who said they would buy it. To calculate the annual population demand, here is as follows.

Table 6. Projected Demand per 45 grams

Year	Projected Demand
2019	1,457,215
2020	1,500,931
2021	1,545,959
2022	1,592,338
2023	1,640,108

$$\text{Projected Annual Demand} = \text{Projected Annual Population} \times \text{Market Acceptability} \times \text{Frequency Agreement} \times 4 \text{ weeks} \times 12 \text{ months}$$

Supply

Historical Supply

Starting a new business does not guarantee success, and to understand how business can meet the increasing market needs, a supply analysis is conducted. Measuring the business’ capability can create enough interest in the market and how much product the company can make in a certain time period.

Table 7. Historical Supply

Supply	Mayumi Organics		Sunsilk Shampoo		Pantene Shampoo	
	Supply	Growth Rate	Supply	Growth Rate	Supply	Growth Rate
2014	179,865		298,864		264,409	
2015	185,261	3%	310,819	4%	277,629	5%
2016	190,818	3%	323,252	4%	291,510	5%
2017	196,543	3%	336,182	4%	306,085	5%
2018	202,439	3%	349,629	4%	322,145	5%
Average		3%		4%		5%

$$\text{Growth Rate} = \text{Present} - \text{Past} / \text{Past}$$

Table 7 shows the annual average increase of 3% for Mayumi Organics, 4% for Sunsilk Shampoo, and 5% for Pantene Shampoo. Table 9.3 presents the supply trends for Mayumi Organics, Sunsilk Shampoo, and Pantene Shampoo over the years 2014 to 2018. Mayumi Organics added more products each year, going from 179,865 units in 2014 up to 202,439 units in 2018, which shows a steady growth of about 3% every year on average. Sunsilk Shampoo sold more units, increasing from 298,864 units in 2014 to 349,629 units in 2018, and it kept a steady average growth of 4% each year. Pantene Shampoo had the best growth

out of the three brands, increasing from 264,409 units in 2014 to 322,145 units in 2018, with an average yearly growth rate of about 5% each year. All three brands saw a steady increase in supply year after year. Pantene Shampoo had the fastest growth, then came Sunsilk Shampoo, and Mayumi Organics had the slowest growth among them.

Demand and Supply Analysis

Demand Gap

Table 8. Demand Gap

Year	Demand	Supply	Demand-Supply Gap	Market Shares (40%)
2019	1,457,215	743,138	714,077	285,631
2020	1,500,931	773,709	727,222	290,889
2021	1,545,959	805,580	740,379	296,152
2022	1,592,338	838,810	753,528	301,411
2023	1,640,108	874,213	765,895	306,358

Table 8 shows that Essentiels Corporation has a room for supplying its product at Talon II, City of Las Piñas, Philippines. Despite having a big competitor, Essentiels Corporation could enter the market along with them.

Market Share of Competitor

Table 9. Market Share of Competitor

Market Share	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Mayumi Organics	208,512	214,768	221,211	227,847	234,682
Sunsilk Shampoo	363,614	378,159	393,285	409,016	425,377
Pantene Shampoo	338,252	355,165	372,923	391,569	411,148
Divided Total Demand	1,457,215	1,500,931	1,545,959	1,592,338	1,640,108
Market Share – Mayumi Organics	14%	14%	14%	14%	14%
Market Share – Sunsilk Shampoo	25%	25%	25%	25%	25%
Market Share – Pantene Shampoo	23%	24%	24%	25%	25%

The market share data in Table 9 shows that Mayumi Organics kept a steady 14% share over the five years, with no changes in its standing in the market. Sunsilk Shampoo kept a 25% share of the market every year, showing it was a reliable and well-known brand in the industry. On the other hand, Pantene Shampoo saw slow but steady growth in its market share, going from 23% in the first year to 24% over the next two years, and finally reaching 25% in the last two years. Overall, Mayumi Organics and Sunsilk Shampoo kept their market shares the same, but Pantene Shampoo slowly improved its position in the competition over time.

Price Study

Table 10 shows the price study for the 45-gram product. The total cost that changes with each unit produced is ₱84.77. This includes ₱80.00 for materials (coconut oil, olive oil, castor oil, lye, water, tea tree oil, rosemary oil, and peppermint oil), which breaks down into ₱32.00 for raw materials, ₱38.00 for packaging, and ₱10.00 for the sticker label. The remaining ₱4.77 is for direct labor, which is calculated by dividing the total labor cost of ₱140,385 by the number of units made each month, which is 29,400. In addition, the total fixed cost each month is ₱38,000.00, which includes rent of ₱24,000.00 and utilities of

₱14,000.00. When spread over 29,400 units, the fixed cost per unit is ₱1.29. If the product is sold for ₱169.00 each and the total cost to make each unit is subtracted, then each unit has a contribution margin of ₱82.94. This means about 49% of the price would contribute toward paying fixed costs and making a profit.

Table 10. Price Study

Price Breakdown	
Variable Cost	45 grams
Raw Materials	₱32.00
Packaging Costs	38.00
Sticker Label	10.00
Total Material Cost	80.00
Direct Labor	140,385
Production in Units	29,400
Direct Labor in Units	4.77
Total Variable Cost	₱84.77
Fixed Cost	
Rent Expense	₱24,000.00
Utilities	14,000.00
Total Fixed Cost	38,000.00
Production Per-Month	29,400.00
Total Fixed Cost in Units	₱1.29
Desired Selling Price	₱169.00
Less: Variable Cost	86.06
Total Contribution Margin in Unit	₱82.94
Total Contribution in unit	51%
Divided by Desired Selling Price	₱169.00
Total Contribution Margin	49%

Marketing Program Product

Essentiels is a product to watch out for. The quality and benefits people get from their local shampoos that they use are the same, but Essentiels is 100% organic and has a cause, and that is to help the environment. Our product wants to eliminate the usage of plastics that is currently being used by almost every shampoo brand in the market, which is harming our home and earth. Our product is a shampoo bar and will be packaged in a tin can, which is a recyclable material.

Our packaging will have a minimalist design which will catch the customers' attention quickly because it is high quality and has a class design. It will look like it is expensive but in reality, it will be just a cheap high-quality product. And for our product itself, it will be an eye catching to our customers because of its bright colors that will make them look for more. The product will also have a soothing smell that customers will love.

Price

Essentiels Shampoo Bars will have different scents, but the price for different variants remain the same. Based on our calculations from the packaging to the product and adding a little bit of profit, we came up with the idea of selling it at ₱169 only. The shampoo bar is good for 40 up to 45 washes, so it will just cost ₱3.38 - ₱3.75 each use. Essentiels Shampoo Bars is 100% organic and at ₱169 it is very cheap. Based on our predictions, we are 293%+ cheaper than our competitors, while Lush is selling theirs for ₱495.

Place

Essentiels plans to have its own actual store, and it will be located at San Beda Homes in Talon, Las Piñas City. It will be a good location for a business like ours because it is along Alabang – Zapote Road, which is the national road of Las Piñas. It means that the people who live in Las Piñas City and people who pass through the city would easily catch and locate the store. The location is also surrounded by establishments like city hall, a university, malls, fast food chains, and banks. Other than the actual store, Essentiels, will also have its own booth at the biggest Christmas Bazaar in Manila, which is the Noel’s Bazaar, including other bazaars.

Promotion

Essentiels plans to promote the shampoo bars, such as social media boosts, social media influencers, and local Filipino celebrities. Social media has this feature that can turn your post into an advertisement and boost it. So, by just scrolling through Facebook timeline, people will see the post automatically and it will help Essentiels reach its prospective customers. Essentiels will hire social media influencers that have high engagements on social media. Partnering up with these people will help Essentiels to help spread the benefits of using our product and the awareness of reducing the usage of plastics and also to sell the shampoo bars itself. Aside from social media influencers, local Filipino celebrities have a bigger influence here in the Philippines. By having a partnership with them, that would have a huge impact to the market.

SWOT Analysis

SWOT analysis helps a company especially the ones that is just starting like Essentiels to identify what will be the position of the company in the market. It is important for a company to know its own strengths and weaknesses and the possible opportunities and threats that will come up. By that, the company would easily know when and what to improve internally and externally.

Figure 1. SWOT Analysis

Conclusions and Recommendations

Majority of the respondents conveyed their unawareness of our product, yet in spite of this, they were still willing to try our product. Based on the business demand-gap analysis, there is a strong and sufficient market for our product.

Majority of our respondents are yet unaware of our Essentiels Shampoo Bar as it is still quite new to them. Based on our survey, 76% of our respondents are willing to try our product and 70% are willing to spend Php151.00-Php200.00 for our product. 84% of our respondents choose a shampoo for its effectiveness. 76% of our respondents would prefer to use an organic kind of shampoo. Most of our respondents based their choice of shampoo through the effects of it. Most of our respondents buy their shampoo from retail stores.

For the development and improvement of our study, the following are our recommendations:

- We should be able to infuse a sufficient amount of capital for the support of our operational requirements.
- Everyone in our company should follow its rules and regulations for its smooth day-to-day operations.
- Should there be an increase in our sales, the proponents should consider expanding their business.
- Our company should endeavor to continuously make improvements and further innovate their product.

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